

Tetravalent Manganese as an Oxidising Agent

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TETRAVALENT manganese in the form of manganese dioxide is known as an oxidising agent for the oxidation of hydrochloric acid to chlorine, Fe(II) to Fe(III) and oxalic acid to carbon dioxide and water. MnO₂ by itself does not dissolve easily in sulphuric acid but in the presence of reductants it can be rapidly brought into solution. Stauter and Um¹ in a recent patent suggested the possibility of employing manganese dioxide ores for converting Cr(III) of the chrome ore to Cr(VI). However, there are no reports on the use of Mn(IV) solution as an oxidimetric reagent till recently², due to the difficulties in the preparation of a fairly stable solution. During the study of the kinetics of the decomposition of permanganate in sulphuric acid by spectrophotometric methods, Mandal and Sant³ reported that in 8-11 M sulphuric acid, Mn(IV) is formed according to the equation :

The manganese(IV) solution thus formed is reasonably stable, and the change in normality of a 0.1 N solution is only 0.1-0.2 percent per day at 25°. Such a solution is a powerful oxidising agent and the standard potential of the redox system Mn(IV)+2 e⁻ ⇌ Mn(II) is 1.577 V.

Manganese(IV) sulphate as an oxidimetric reagent :

This reagent has been used for the titrimetric determination of a number of reducing agents. For instance Fe(II), V(IV), U(IV) and Mo(V)⁵ are quantitatively oxidised respectively to Fe(III), V(V), U(VI) and Mo(VI) in 1-2 M sulphuric acid and titrations can be performed using ferroin as the indicator. Oxalate is oxidised to carbon dioxide and water in 1-2 M sulphuric acid and titrations with Mn(IV) are possible at 70°. Arsenite is quantitatively oxidised to arsenate by Mn(IV) in hydrochloric acid medium with iodide ion as the catalyst. Mandal³ reported the use of iodide or iodate as a catalyst, with Mn(IV) colour itself indicating the end point. It has been found by the present authors that with iodine monochloride as a catalyst methyl orange could be used as an indicator.

Manganese(IV) sulphate solution quantitatively oxidises antimony(III) to antimony(V) in the presence of an halogen acid and titrations can be carried out using methyl orange as an indicator. Methyl orange is a better indicator than ferroin⁶ in a semiaqueous solution containing hydrochloric acid and iodine monochloride. Further, ferroin end points are not reliable due to the fact that ferroin forms insoluble complex with Sb(V)⁷. In sulphuric acid medium and in the absence of chloride, both As(III) and Sb(III) reduce manganese(IV) to manganese(III) and indirect titrations by adding excess manganese(IV) and back titrations with iron(III) show good agreement with those of direct titrations.

Manganese dioxide as an oxidation-decomposition agent :

It has been observed that MnO₂ can be conveniently used as a decomposition agent for the analysis of refractory ores like chromite and sulphide ores like chalcopyrite. Either the synthetically⁸ prepared MnO₂ or the naturally occurring manganese ore can be employed for the purpose.

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